

Determination of Zinc with Cupric Ion-Selective Electrode and its Analytical Application in Fertilizers

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The results of potentiometric titration of Zn(II) with cupric ion-selective electrode in the presence of ammonia buffer solution are recorded. The best results for determination of Zn(II) are obtained in 0.1 M ammonia buffer. Samples containing 1.5 μ moles in 5 ml to 6 μ moles in 10 ml solution could be analysed. Results compare favourably with other methods.

The application of the method for determination of zinc in fertilizers is demonstrated.

ONE of the main advantages of ion-selective electrode used in the potentiometric titrations lies in the development of indirect methods for determination of such anions or cations which themselves are not sensor of electrodes¹⁻³.

In the course of our investigation with ion-selective electrode we tried to apply the method of Baumman and Wallace¹ for indirect determination of Zn(II) using cupric ion-selective electrode. However, the results obtained proved to be quite unsatisfactory. An equivalent part of the titration curve could not be obtained.

If α -coefficient of the Zn(II) and Cu(II) side reactions in ammonia buffer⁴ are taken into consideration, one could arrive at the conclusion that the inequality $K'_{Zn-EDTA} > K'_{Cu-EDTA}$ remains valid ($K'_{Zn-EDTA}$ and $K'_{Cu-EDTA}$ are the adequate conditional constants). The chemical equilibrium accounting for the inflection point, which coincides with the equivalent point is presented in the reaction.

In an acidic medium where $K'_{Zn-EDTA} < K'_{Cu-EDTA}$, more of indicator Cu-EDTA might prove necessary for the reaction¹ and the curve is not well defined.

In ammonia medium, where $K'_{Zn-EDTA} > K'_{Cu-EDTA}$, a single drop of indicator Cu-EDTA is enough for the displacement of cupric ions.

Experimental

Apparatus: All measurements were made using Seibold Cupric Ion Activity Electrode, Model 29-17, Ag/AgCl double junction reference electrode with 0.1 M KNO₃ in the outer compartment and the Seibold Model G 104 digital pH/mV meter. A glass electrode with the same reference was used to ascertain pH of the solutions.

Reagents: The indicator Cu-EDTA was prepared according to the reported method⁵. The final solution contained 0.5 M Cu-EDTA with pH 4.09. The titrant, 0.1 M Na₂HEDTA was prepared from 0.1 M Na₂H₂EDTA.2H₂O and 0.1 M NaOH. Buffer

solution NH₄⁺/NH₃ with concentrations 1 M, 0.1 M and 0.05 M were used for keeping the pH constant between 7.5 and 8. Ammonium nitrate containing microamount of zinc as ZnO was used. Zn(NO₃)₂ and Cu(NO₃)₂ were added to the impure carbamide.

Determination of Zn(II) in solutions: The diluted solution of zinc (10⁻³ M) in ammonium medium was prepared just before the determination. An aliquot (3.00 to 10.00 ml) was drawn from this solution and transferred into a plastic beaker. One drop of 0.5 M indicator Cu-EDTA was added. The electrodes were immersed into the solution and the solution titrated with 0.01 M Na₂HEDTA. A microburette of 2.000 $\pm$ 0.005 ml was used. The rate of titration was 0.01 ml/10 sec with constant stirring (50 rev/min).

Determination of Zn(II) in fertilizers: To a sample containing $\sim$ 1.0 g NH₄NO₃ or 0.5 g CO(NH₂)₂ were added 1-2 drops of HNO₃ (1:1) and 10.0 ml 1 M ammonia buffer. The mixture was diluted with double distilled water up to the mark. An aliquot of 5.00 ml was titrated in the presence of 1 drop of Cu-EDTA indicator with the cupric ion-selective electrode.

Fig. 1. Zn(II) titration with Cu-selective electrode at different concentration of the buffer [7.00 ml Zn(II) 0.563.10⁻³ M].

TABLE 1—REPRODUCIBILITY AND ACCURACY OF THE RESULTS OBTAINED FROM POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF Zn(II) WITH CUPRIC ION-SELECTIVE ELECTRODE, USING Cu-EDTA AS INDICATOR

Buffer concentration <i>M</i>	Zn(II) Taken μ moles	Mean, $\bar{x}$ μ moles	$d_t = \frac{\sum(\bar{x} - x_t)}{n}$	$S_{\bar{x}} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum(\bar{x} - x_t)^2}}{n-1}$	$\%S = \frac{S_{\bar{x}}}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100$
0.1	3.94	4.02	0.085	0.0106	0.26
0.5	4.26	4.33	0.121	0.1634	3.77
0.2	1.22	1.17	0.116	0.133	11.4

Results and Discussions

The effect of concentration of the buffer solutions on the titration of Zn(II) is shown in Fig. 1. Statistical analyses of some of the results are presented in Table 1. It is shown that the concentration of the buffer solution of 0.1 *M* is the best medium for the titration.

TABLE 2—THE EFFECT OF INTERFERING IONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF Zn(II) BY POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION WITH CUPRIC ION-SELECTIVE ELECTRODE

Interfering ions, <i>M</i>	M/Zn	Zn(II) μ moles	
		Obtained	Taken
K ⁺	120	3.94	3.94
Ca ²⁺	120	3.93	3.94
SO ₄ ²⁻	120	3.95	3.94
Cl ⁻	100	3.95	3.94
NO ₃ ⁻	100	3.95	3.94
Ba ²⁺	100	3.96	3.94
CO(NH ₂) ₂	100	3.96	3.94

Fig. 2. Determination of Zn(II) in fertilizers with Cu-selective electrode in 0.1*M* ammonia buffer solution; Curve 1—Zn(II) in NH₄NO₃ and Curve 2—Zn(II) in CO(NH₂)₂.

The effect of interfering ions on the equivalence point of titration curves are shown in Table 2. 120 times SO₄²⁻ ion, present in excess does not affect the result using Cu electrode, but using Cd electrode³, only 10 times SO₄²⁻ excess is tolerated.

TABLE 3—STATISTICAL ANALYSES OF THE RESULTS OF DETERMINATION OF Zn(II) IN FERTILIZERS

Statistical analyses	Zn(II) in NH ₄ NO ₃ %	Zn(II) in CO(NH ₂) ₂ mol/l × 10 ⁴
mean, $\bar{x}$	0.995	0.560
$d_t = \frac{\sum(\bar{x} - x_t)}{n}$	0.0008	0.002
$\%d_t = \frac{d_t}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100$	0.084	0.036
$S_{\bar{x}} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum(\bar{x} - x_t)^2}}{n-1}$	0.001	0.0025
$\%S = \frac{S_{\bar{x}}}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100$	0.1	0.045
$1/4S_{\bar{x}}$	0.00015	0.0006

The application of the method for determination of Zn(II) in fertilizers is shown in Fig. 2 and Table 3. Complexometric titration and atomic absorption were used as comparative methods.

References

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